

DIETARY SUPPLEMENTS MADE FROM MIXTURE OF MICROORGANISMS**Boranbayeva G.,***PhD student***Abzhalelov A.,***Doctor of Biological Sciences***Temirkhanov A.,***Candidate of Agricultural Sciences***Tekebayeva Zh.***PhD student**Eurasian National University, Astana, Kazakhstan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7584591>**Abstract**

Live bacteria known as probiotics can help the host's health when given in sufficient doses. The use of probiotics in chicken has expanded gradually over the years due to higher demand for antibiotic-free poultry. This systematic study aims to summarize and assess the effects of probiotics on the digestion, immunology, and growth and laying performance, gut histomorphology, and gut microbiota of chicken. An electronic search was conducted using relevant keywords to include literature pertaining to the topic. Under the current commercial production conditions, the performance and gut health of chicken were critically evaluated for 17 regularly used probiotic species. According to the findings, probiotic supplementation may have the following effects: 1. Altering the gut microbiota, 2. Promoting.

Keywords: probiotics, microorganisms, poultry, dietary supplements, bacteria, microbiota, strain.

Introduction

Since more than 50 years ago, antibiotics have been used to preserve animal health, foster growth, and increase productivity. However, experts began to express alarm about the emergence of bacteria resistant to the medicines streptomycin and tetracycline, which were used in turkeys and broilers, respectively, as early as the 1950s. These results paved the way for agricultural authorities to enact stronger regulatory restrictions on the use of antibiotics in chicken feeds. Live microorganisms called probiotics are added to animal feed as supplements or as feed additives. Probiotics, also referred to as direct-fed microorganisms, are beneficial to the host and work primarily via influencing the animal's gastrointestinal tract (GIT). Through improvements to gut health and nutrient utilization, probiotic supplementation in the food can enhance animal health and performance. Probiotic supplementation, for instance, has been shown to help farm animals by improving their immune systems, altering their structural makeup, and producing more cytokines, which protect the intestinal mucosa from pathogens. Popular in the business, *Bacillus subtilis* has been demonstrated to increase intestinal villus height [1]. The digestion and absorption of nutrients can be improved by raising the villus height and crypt structure in the GIT. Important defenses against harmful microorganisms and cellular homeostasis are maintained by tight junctions. In the chicken sector, heat stress can be a significant environmental concern. The bird's internal core temperature fluctuates beyond what is comfortable under heat stress. Through behavioral and physiological adaptation processes, poultry will try to balance its heat production and dissipation in order to overcome such obstacles.

The purpose of the work: **to show the importance of increasing the quality of poultry meat, to reach the peak of meat productivity in a short time, and to cause a decrease in poultry waste by actively feeding probiotic biological products in poultry farming.**

Due to their wide range of positive effects, such as fostering growth and production, enhancing immunity, and protecting health, feed additives and nutritional supplements are becoming more and more important in the poultry industry as well as in healthcare systems. Moreover, non-nutritional variables such as sanitation, processing of feed components, ambient temperature, animal health and genetic composition have an influence on animal performance. Nowadays, it is of great importance to develop sets of veterinary measures aimed at increasing the life span and productivity of birds through the targeted use of pharmacological, environmentally friendly drugs and biologically active substances.

Main body

Probiotics are live microorganisms introduced into animal diets as feed additives. Adding probiotics to the diet improves bird health and performance by contributing to gut health and nutrient utilization. For example, it has been proven that probiotic supplements are beneficial to farm animals in terms of immunomodulation, structural modulation, and have a positive effect on the intestinal mucosa against pathogens [2].

Traditionally, dry food without microorganisms is used for feeding. The use of microorganisms with the necessary properties in obtaining live bio-food is of great practical importance. Introducing new types of biofeeds into production using microorganisms

(probiotics) is currently important for the development of poultry farming in Kazakhstan.

In the course of comparative work with chickens of the control group, it was found that vitamin E affects the immune organs of birds, increases the mass and size of internal organs, increases the strength of cells in the blood body [3].

Administration of succinic acid to the organism in poultry farming helps to increase the resistance of the organism, the bactericidal and lysozyme activity of blood serum by 10.4% and 18.2%, stimulates embryonic and postembryonic development, and increases the incubation capacity of chickens by 10% [3].

Preparations of succinic acid are commercially available and available on sale - "Yantavit", "Yantarin", "Yantarin Formula 2", "Vitar-S" preparations are vitamin complexes considered as biologically active supplements (BAS) for poultry.

Minerals are part of complex organic compounds that perform various physiological and metabolic functions in the body. Animals take them with food and partly with water. Deficiency or excess of some elements in feed leads to a decrease in productivity and fertility, worsens feed utilization, causes various diseases [4-7].

Feed additives for birds can be purchased at any specialized store. However, most chicken and chicken producers use them cautiously to feed poultry. But experts conclude that it is possible and necessary to introduce them into the diet of birds. In addition, food should be balanced in terms of proteins, fats, and carbohydrates. It should also contain a sufficient amount of vitamins and trace elements, because their lack, unfortunately, leads to a number of serious diseases of birds.

The daily ration of chickens should include grain, bran, dry grass, juicy feed, bone meal, and dry protein feed. All components should be given in a certain proportion in the diet. Even when the required level of balance is reached, it is very difficult to provide chickens with all the necessary amino acids, vitamins, and minerals. This applies especially to the spring-winter period. In addition, the introduction of expensive products into the diet significantly increases the cost of chicken meat and eggs. It is for these reasons that poultry farmers now prefer to actively introduce feed additives into the daily menu of birds [8-11].

Early feed availability in starter diets for chickens was studied by us during 30 days after they were born. We discovered that broilers' growth performance can be improved by early feeding. Concepts for hatching, such on-farm hatching, offer a chance to give freshly hatched birds the best nourishment possible, supporting their growth and the formation of a healthy gut.

The projected results from adding brown algae to one of the diets to improve growth performance, organ development, gut microbiome, and vaccine-induced antibody responses were not achieved [12].

Materials and methodology.

The experiment was held in Astana, in the Laboratory of "Republican Collection of Microorganisms".

There were used several methods such as microbiology, molecular-biology and biotechnology.

Screening of cultures of micro-organisms, which are of the greatest industrial value as a probiotic supplement to feed, was carried out.

To accomplish this task, lactic acid bacteria (LAB) with a confirmed genetic identification based on the analysis of the 16S RNA gene were requested from the collection of the Biobank of Industrial Microorganisms of "the Republican Collection of Microorganisms". Biobank provided 27 LAB cultures.

For the primary screening, viability values (VVS) of LAB cultures were assessed using the Miles&Misra method. This indicator is important, since one of the requirements for probiotics is stable growth in sufficient cell titers. An estimate of the maximum GSP for selection among crops was given. The optimal figures for the selection of probiotic microorganisms is the GSP index of 107 CFU/ml or more.

As a result of the primary screening, 7 collection strains of bacteria of the genus *Lactobacillus*, *Pediococcus*, *Lactococcus* and yeast of the genus *Saccharomyces* were taken for further work with a preliminary assessment of the GSP numbers, which amounted to 106-107.

Studies have been carried out, including the study of the cultural, biochemical and physiological properties of selected strains of microorganisms as probiotics:

The study of morphology and tinctorial properties of cultures. Light immersion microscopy of LSD was performed at x100 magnification (Micros, Austria). Gram staining showed the presence of Gram-positive short and long rods, as well as non-spore-forming coccoid bacteria with negative growth on meat-peptone agar. The microscopic picture of the smears is shown in Table 1. Testing of isolated LAB isolates for catalase and oxidase activity showed a negative reaction.

Study of the cultural properties of the strain.

The cultural properties of microorganisms are determined by inoculation on liquid, semi-liquid and solid media. On liquid media, the degree and nature of turbidity of the broth, the size, shape and consistency of the precipitate, the presence or absence of a film on the surface of the medium are taken into account.

For the cultivation of cultures of lactobacilli used enriched media MPC-1 broth manufactured by HiMedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. (India) and MPC-4 dense media manufactured by HiMedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. (India). The cultural characteristics of LAB were exactly homogeneous colonies of white or whitish-milky color, with smooth edges and a convex surface, with a sour-milk smell and are presented in Table 1.

Bacteria showed growth both on liquid and solid nutrient media. The grown colonies were sifted into test tubes with MPC-agar nutrient medium and incubated at optimal temperatures for 48 hours for storage.

All LAB cultures were cryopreserved at -80°C in a protective medium containing 70% nutrient medium, 20% glycerol, and 10% sucrose.

Study of the physiological and biochemical properties of the strain. The study of the ability of

bacteria to ferment carbohydrates is used for the identification and differential diagnosis of microorganisms. The *saccharolytic* activity of the strains was studied using carbohydrate disks manufactured by HiMedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. (India) DD013-1VL Sucrose, DD002-1VL Glucose, DD005-1VL Maltose, DD007-1VL Mannose, DD010-1VL Rhamnose, DD001-1VL Arabinose, DD014-1VL Xylose, DD029-1VL Raffinose, DD030-1VL Melibiose Lact, DD004 designed to differentiate microorganisms, according to their ability to ferment carbohydrates.

The proposed production strain must fully comply with the properties of the type strains of the species according to the modern classification of the Bergey Bacteria Key.

One of the important factors in screening for probiotic preparations is antagonism to various pathogenic and opportunistic microorganisms [13-14].

In our studies, antagonistic activity was studied against such test strains as *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538 B-RKM 0470, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922B-RKM 0447, *Enterococcus faecium*, *Salmonella enteritidis* B-RKM 0680 from the collection of the Biobank of Industrial Microorganisms of the Republican Collection microorganisms.

The study of antagonistic activity was performed by the method of diffusion into agar [15]; for this, a suspension of cells of daily cultures of LAB is prepared in an amount of 1 mld / 1 ml (according to the standard of bacterial turbidity) and applied to the surface of the dish with the medium. Next, wells with a top diameter of 10 mm are cut out and filled with cultures of test strains (0.1 ml). A day later, the diameter of the zone of absence of bacterial growth is measured.

The results of the antagonistic activity of the studied objects are presented in Table 1, low activity - 1.0-4.9 mm, medium - 5.0-8.9, high - more than 9 mm. The inactive group included cultures that did not suppress test strains.

Most of the cultures showed a high value of antagonistic activity to the pathogens *Enterococcus faecium* and *Salmonella enteritidis*: the width of the zones of growth inhibition exceeded 9 mm. Only *Pediococcus pentosaceus* F-1 B-RKM showed a high degree of antagonism to all test strains. The strain *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* 6A-K25 B-RKM 0098 was the weakest antagonist.

Studies have been carried out, including the study of the cultural, biochemical and physiological properties of selected strains of microorganisms as probiotics.

Study of morphology and tinctorial properties of cultures.

Light immersion microscopy of LSD was performed at x100 magnification (Micros, Austria). Gram staining showed the presence of Gram-positive short and long rods, as well as non-spore forming *coccoid* bacteria with negative growth on meat-peptone agar. The microscopic picture of the smears is shown in Table 2. Testing of isolated LAB isolates for catalase and oxidase activity showed a negative reaction.

Study of the cultural properties of the strain.

The cultural properties of microorganisms are determined by sowing them on liquid, semi-liquid and solid media. On liquid media, the degree and nature of turbidity of the broth, the size, shape and consistency of the precipitate, the presence or absence of a film on the surface of the medium are taken into account.

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Study of the physiological and biochemical properties of the strain.

The study of the ability of bacteria to ferment carbohydrates is used for the identification and differential diagnosis of microorganisms. The *saccharolytic* activity of the strains was studied using carbohydrate disks manufactured by HiMedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. (India) DD013-1VL Sucrose, DD002-1VL Glucose, DD005-1VL Maltose, DD007-1VL Mannose, DD010-1VL Rhamnose, DD001-1VL Arabinose, DD014-1VL Xylose, DD029-1VL Raffinose, DD030-1VL Melibiose Lact, DD004 intended for the differentiation of microorganisms, according to their ability to ferment carbohydrates (Table 2).

The proposed production strain must fully correspond in these properties to the type strains of the species according to the modern classification of Bergey's Bacterial Key [16]. Strains with unclear characteristics cannot be recommended as probiotics.

Table 1.

Cultural-morphological and physiological properties of selected strains

№	Name of strain	Cultural-morphological properties		Physiological properties
		On a liquid medium	On a solid medium	
1.	B-RKM 0357 <i>Lactococcus lactis</i> L 18	strong, whitish-milky color	Gram+ cocci are grouped in pairs and short chains, forming white, convex colonies with smooth edges.	pH 6.3 - 6.9 Optimum growth temperature 30 °C;
2.	B-RKM 0358 <i>Lactococcus lactis</i> L 6	Strong, whitish-milky color	Gram + cocci are grouped in pairs and short chains, convex colonies with smooth edges.	pH 6.3 - 6.9 Optimum growth temperature 30 °C;
3.	B-RKM 0042 <i>Lactococcus lactis</i> subsp. <i>lactis</i> TG-1/TMa/	Strong, whitish-milky color	Gram-positive rods arranged in chains and clusters The colonies are superficial, smooth, round in shape, white in color, the consistency is soft, the edges are even, the borders are clear, some merge, small sizes.	pH6.3 - 6.9, Optimum growth temperature 30 °C;
4.	B-RKM 0044 <i>Lactococcus delbrueckii</i> subsp. <i>lactis</i> CF-1/KRMa/	Strong, whitish-milky color	Gram-positive rods arranged in chains and clusters The colonies are superficial, smooth, round in shape, white in color, the consistency is soft, the edges are even, the borders are clear, some merge, small sizes	pH.4–4.6 Optimum growth temperature 40-44 °C
5.	B-RKM 0348 <i>Lactobacillus brevis</i> L 9	Strong, whitish-milky color	Gram-positive rods arranged in chains and clusters. The colonies are superficial, smooth, round in shape, white in color, the consistency is soft, the edges are even, the borders are clear, some merge, small sizes.	pH 4.5 Optimum growth temperature 30°C
6.	B-RKM 0098 <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> 6A-K25	Strong, whitish-milky color	Gram+, uniform oval individual cells, 5-9 µm in size, with a thick cell wall. Colonies are white-cream in color, round, shiny, convex, dome-shaped, diameter 1-3 mm, smooth edges, smooth surface, dense consistency	pH 5.0 Optimum growth temperature 29°C
7.	B-RKM 0935 <i>Pediococcus pentosaceus</i> F-1	Strong, whitish-milky color	Gram + cocci, milky colonies, shiny, round, opaque, smooth edges, diameter 0.5-1.5 mm.	pH 6.0–6.5 Optimum growth temperature 37°C

Table 2.

Saccharolytic activity of strains

Name os strain	Glucose	Lactose	Galose	Fructose	Arabinose	Ribose	Melibiose	Raffinose	Maltose	Sucrose	Xylose	Rhamnoza	Mannose	Catalase	oxidase
B-RKM 0348	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
B-RKM 0357	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	-
B-RKM 0358	+	+	-	+		+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	-
B-RKM 0042	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	-
B-RKM 0044	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	-
B-RKM 0098	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
B-RKM 0935	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-

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later, the diameter of the zone of absence of bacterial growth is measured.

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Name of strains	Antagonistic activity (mm)			
	<i>Salm.ent.</i>	<i>St.aur.</i>	<i>Ent.faec.</i>	<i>E.coli</i>
B-RKM 0044 <i>Lactococcus delbrueckii</i> subsp. <i>lactis</i> CF-1/KRMa	12,0±1	0	15±1.2	16±2.1
B-RKM 0358 <i>Lactococcus lactis</i> L 6	13±1	0	18.0±2.0	14±1
B-RKM 0357 <i>Lactococcus lactis</i> L 18	11±0,3	0	16±2.1	26±1
B-RKM 0042 <i>Lactococcus lactis</i> subsp. <i>lactis</i> TF-1/TMa/	12,33±0,58	19±1.0	21±1.5	0
B-RKM 0348 <i>Lactobacillus brevis</i> L 9	14,6±0,4	19±1.0	21±1.5	0
B-RKM 0935 <i>Pediococcus pentosaceus</i> F-1	11±0,3	20.0±3.6	19±1.0	13±1
B-RKM 0098 <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> 6A-K25	0	0	0	14±1

Conclusion

The screening of microbial cultures, which are of the greatest industrial value as a probiotic feed additive, helped to select 7 types of strain.

These strains provide a natural route for the production of feed additives in the poultry industry. In the next 10 years, the population will face a lack of meat, which will cause dissonance among the population including Kazakhstan. Biological active supplements are also increased in price and have antibiotic mixture indeed. Probiotics are regarded as an enticing feed supplement due to its numerous empirical advantages, which include improved gut microbiological equilibrium, immunological response, growth, and laying performance. As probiotics might partially replace the use of some subtherapeutic antibiotics, the use of probiotics in chicken production may partially solve the public health concerns about the emergence of antimicrobial resistance. Studies revealed a wide range of diversity in the advantages experienced due to the variations in the experimentation procedures. With the help of tested strains there could be more than 10 types of BAS oriented for specific country in poultry leading to other types of stock raising.

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